

IMPACT OF FUNDING IN THE ORGANIZATION OF SPORTS FOR THE DISABLED PERSONS IN SPECIAL SCHOOLS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The Nigeria National Education Policy (6-3-3-4) is specific on physical education when it stated in paragraph 7 and 8 of section one of the National Policy on Education that physical education will be emphasized at all levels of the educational system. In an attempt to further confirm the attention given to sport in Nigeria, the federal government of Nigeria's Sports Development Policy documents (FRN, 1989) states that the Federal government accepts special responsibility for ensuring adequate level of funding for such programme as sports for the disabled. Very little efforts have been made in respect of proper funding for sports for the disabled in special schools in Nigeria. This paper discussed the impact of funding in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria. The hypothesis stated in this paper was that funding has no significant impact in the organization of sport for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria. The population of this study consists of 5030 disabled students, 38 sports coordinators and 35 coaches of Special Schools in Nigeria. Proportionate sampling technique was used in selecting the number of respondents while simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents from each of the special schools using the dip and pick method. A sample size of four hundred and eight (408) respondents made up of disabled persons in special schools, sports coordinators and coaches were used. A designed questionnaire for the deaf and dumb, the crippled were administered while the blind were equally administered with questionnaire which was interpreted into braille. The result in table 1 indicated the calculated chi-square value of 441.18 to be higher than the critical chi-square value of 34.17 at df 20 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. This shows that funding has significant

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impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that funding has no significant impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria is hereby rejected.

Keywords: disabled persons, funding, impact, organization, special schools, sports

1. Introduction

People with physical disabilities do not participate in sports as regularly as those without disabilities. For example, in the United States, nearly two-thirds of people with physical disabilities do not participate in sports, whereas just over one-third of people without disabilities do participate in sports. Sports can be defined as 'an activity involving physical exertion with or without a game or competition elements, with a minimal duration of 30 minutes for at least two times a week, and where skills and physical endurance are either required or to be improved. The physical benefits of sports have been frequently documented. Several studies noted the potential for sports to decrease the risk of secondary health conditions such as heart disease, diabetes type II and obesity, especially for individual program participants. It is therefore important to understand what prevents or stimulates people with physical disabilities to participate in sports. Insight into the barriers and facilitators in this respect can also help in providing opportunities to increase sports participation among people with physical disabilities.

The Nigeria National Education Policy (6-3-3-4) is specific on physical education when it stated in paragraph 7 and 8 of section one of the National Policy on Education that physical education will be emphasized at all levels of the educational system. In an attempt to further confirm the attention given to sport in Nigeria, the federal government of Nigeria's Sports Development Policy documents (FRN, 1989) states that the Federal government accepts special responsibility for ensuring adequate level of funding for such programme as sports for the disabled. Very little efforts have been made in respect of proper funding for sports for the disabled in special schools in Nigeria. No matter how government and relevant the sports programme of the disabled are, their objectives would not be realized if adequate fund is not made for the programmes. This in turn makes it impossible for the disabled to fully develop their potentials within the sports programme. With proper funding, sports for the disabled will be able to justify its inclusion in the special school curriculum in Nigeria in terms of proper accountability especially in these days of dwindling government resources.

Haggerty (2005) stated that sports have many areas that need organization decision making, these decisions are essentially funding decision since money is needed to achieve stated objectives. Thus, the concerned agencies need to double their efforts in the provision of funds that would ensure sports for the disabled are organized

regularly. Thus, this would be their level of acceptance and integrated in schools and society.

Ekanem (2004) opined that funds is the major factor which many things depend on. He further stated that money is needed in construction of facilities and purchase new equipment, paying of sports personnel and advertising sports programme of special school sports.

2. Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, some notable disabled persons had their foundations of participating in sports specifically from Special School Sports where they were discovered as talents and further moved to compete for Nigeria in the Para-lympics. Furthermore, the disabled persons living with one deformity or the other are often treated with contempt, disregarded, stigmatized and in most cases totally abandoned as harbingers of evil, seen as a mistake of nature that should not be given the same care and love as with normal children (Collins, 1997). Despite all the negative names and stigma ascribed to them, they are committed and determined people who have treaded where able athletes could not, who have achieved and brought more glories to Nigeria than any other group of people (Adeyanju, 2006). Unfortunately, in Nigeria, majority with disability do not have access and opportunity to participate in sport, while few of the disabled persons have taken the bold step of winning medals for Nigeria at various competitive sports at both the Special School Sports and the Paralympics Sports (Adima, 1999).

It is however not clear why some disabled individuals are involved in sports while majority stay away from participation. This research therefore examined the impact of funding in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria.

2.1 Research Questions

The following research question was raised for this study:

- Does funding have any impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria?

2.2 Hypotheses

The following hypothesis was formulated for this study:

- Funding has no significant impact in the organization of sport for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria.

3. Materials and Methods

The population of this study consists of 5030 disabled students, 38 sports coordinators and 35 coaches of Special Schools in Nigeria. Proportionate sampling technique was

used in selecting the number of respondents while simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents from each of the special schools using the dip and pick method. A sample size of four hundred and eight (408) respondents made up of disabled persons in special schools, sports coordinators and coaches were used.

A designed questionnaire for the deaf and dumb; the crippled were administered while the blind were equally administered with questionnaire which was interpreted into braille. Descriptive statistics of frequencies, means, standard deviation and Chi-square were used to analyze the data.

4. Results

Table 1: Mean/SD analysis on funding

S/N	Variables	Mean Score	Standard Dev.	Standard Err	Remarks
1	Funding	3.95	1.08283	.05462	Significant

Decision Mean= 3.50

The null hypothesis states that funding has no significant impact in the organization of sport for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria.

Table 2: Chi-square statistic on funding as an impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria

Variables	X ² calculated	X ² critical	Df	P value
Funding	441.18	34.17	20	0.000

(χ^2 critical =34.17, $P < 0.05$)

The result in table 1 indicated the calculated chi-square value of 441.18 to be higher than the critical chi-square value of 34.17 at df 20 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. This shows that funding has significant impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that funding has no significant impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria is hereby rejected.

5. Discussions

The result of findings in hypothesis one revealed that funding has significant impact in the organization of sports for the disabled persons in special schools in Nigeria. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This finding agrees with Mbaye (1999) where it was stated that at the special schools, less attention was given to sports and that no attention was given to either the disabled persons or the coaches and sports coordinators involved in sports. This lack of attention was attributed to inadequate or complete absence of fund allocation for sports at the special schools.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made for this study:

- The government should provide funds and further set up a monitoring committee involving the disabled persons, sports coordinators, coaches and parents on the utilization of these funds.

6. Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, the following conclusions were made:

- Sports has many areas that need organization decision making, these decisions are essentially funding decision since money is needed to achieve stated objectives. Thus, the concerned agencies need to double their efforts in the provision of funds that would ensure sports for the disabled are organized regularly. Thus, this would be their level of acceptance and integrated in schools and society. Funds are the major factor which many things depend on. He further stated that money is needed in construction of facilities and purchase new equipment, paying of sports personnel and advertising sports programme of special school sports.

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